

Role of surfactants on the mutual solubility of phenol-water system

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The effect of addition of surfactants, namely, sodium dodecyl sulfate (anionic), cetylpyridinium chloride (cationic) and Triton X-100 (nonionic) on the critical solution temperature (CST) of phenol-water system has been studied. The CST of the system which increases initially, decreases with further addition of ionic surfactants, whereas the nonionic surfactant continuously increases the CST. The composition of phenol at CST increases with the increase in concentration of ionic surfactant. An attempt has been made to explain the decrease/increase in CST in terms of micellar interaction.

One of the most instructive ways of discussing the properties of non-ideal solutions is in terms of their deviation from ideality. If the positive deviation from Raoult's law becomes sufficiently large ($\Delta G^E \gg 0$) the components may no longer form a continuous series of solutions, i.e. immiscibility may result. A system will separate into two solution phases if the formation of the two phases results in a more negative value of the Gibbs free energy than if the system formed only a single phase¹. The increase in temperature of such partially miscible liquid systems and addition of suitable substances increase the mutual solubility of the two liquids. Limited informations are available on the effect of surfactants²⁻⁴ on the solubilization of phenol in water and vice versa. So it was considered worthwhile to carry out a systematic investigation on the effect of anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants on the critical solution temperature (CST) of binary liquid system of phenol-water system.

Results and Discussion

The composition of the conjugate solutions of phenol-water vs the miscibility temperature were plotted. At the CST, the composition of phenol was found to be ~34.1% and the CST was 67.7°. Here it may be noted that the literature values of CST and composition vary in the ranges 66.0–68.6° and 32.7–36.5% (by weight) of phenol, which can be due to the impurities present. The data on CST of phenol-water system in the presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate, are summarised in Table 1. The data reveal that the presence of SDS alters the CST of phenol-water system. When a small amount of SDS was present in phenol-water system (conc. of SDS solution was 0.001 M, much lower than that of CMC, $\sim 8.1 \times 10^{-3} M$)² the CST of phenol-water system had gone up by 0.7°, and this increase in CST indicates that SDS at very low concentration behaves like an electrolyte in water and thereby causing salting out. However, it is noteworthy that even though the presence of SDS has increased the CST of phenol-water system, the effect is very much less compared to that of

Na_2SO_4 of the same concentration (Table 1). When an electrolyte is added to water the structure of water is perturbed which in turn decreases the solubility of phenol in water and hence increases the CST of the system. In the case of SDS, may be due to hydrophobic interaction, the effect of ion-solvent/hydrophilic interaction is reduced and thus relatively less increase in CST of the system.

It is interesting to note that as the concentration of SDS in phenol-water system was increased from 0.001 M, the CST of the system (which had increased from 67.5 to 68.2°) started decreasing, and at 0.007 M, the CST of the solution was the same as that of only phenol-water system, i.e. 0.007 M SDS seems to have restored the value of CST of phenol-water system. With the further increase in concentration of SDS (conc. >0.008 M) the CST decreased further. So, from this observation, we are tempted to infer that at 0.007 M SDS the effect of SDS on structure of water (hydrophilic interaction) is counterbalanced by the hydrophobic interaction of SDS or it is plausible that at this concentration the phenol and water molecules must be binding to SDS and this structure might not have any effect on CST. It was noticed that with the addition of SDS, not only the CST of phenol-water system decreased but the concentration of phenol (at CST composition) also increased (from 35.3 to ~50%). It is worth mentioning that at room temperature, phenol-water system can be made homogeneous by the addition of 0.16 M SDS.

It is observed from Table 2 that when about $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ CPC (CMC $\sim 8 \times 10^{-4} M$) is present in phenol-water system, the CST of the system just like in the case of SDS, has increased but the increase in CST of phenol-water system is much higher (from 67.5 to 71.6°) compared to that of SDS of the same concentrations. With the further increase in concentration of CPC, the CST of the system starts decreasing and the concentration of phenol at CST composition starts increasing. It may be noted that even though the effects of SDS and CPC on CST of phenol-water systems are similar, the actual changes in CST are much smaller in the presence of CPC. We do not have any reasonable explanation for the observation.

Table 1. The effect of sodium dodecyl sulfate on CST of phenol-SDS solution*

Sl. no.	Conc. of SDS <i>M</i>	Comp. of phenol (wt%) at CST	CST °C	<i>E</i>
1.	0.000	34.9	67.5	
2.	0.001	35.3 (35.4)	68.2 (71.8)	700
3.	0.002	35.0	67.9	200
4.	0.005	35.2 (35.1)	67.7 (73.1)	40
5.	0.007	35.2	67.5	0
6.	0.008	35.2	66.5	-125
7.	0.010	35.0	65.5 (73.9)	-200
8.	0.050	40.3	51.0	-330
9.	0.100	50.1	32.5	-350
10.	0.160	56.2	25.0	-265

* Values in parenthesis refer to those of sodium sulfate.

Table 2. Effect of cetylpyridinium chloride on CST of phenol-CPC solution

Sl. no.	Conc. of CPC <i>M</i>	Comp. of phenol (wt%) at CST	CST °C
1.	0.0000	34.9	67.5
2.	0.0001	34.1	71.6
3.	0.0002	35.1	71.3
4.	0.0005	35.2	71.0
5.	0.0008	35.3	70.5
6.	0.0010	35.4	70.0
7.	0.0050	35.1	69.0
8.	0.0100	40.2	68.2

Table 3. Effect of Triton X-100 on CST of phenol-triton X-100 solution

Sl. no.	Conc. of TX-100 <i>M</i>	Comp. of phenol (wt%) at CST	CST °C
1.	0.0000	34.9	67.5
2.	0.0001	35.1	72.6
3.	0.0002	35.1	72.8
4.	0.0005	35.4	73.2
5.	0.0008	35.0	74.1
6.	0.0010	35.1	74.6

Addition of Triton X-100 to phenol-water system, increases the CST of the system (Table 3) and unlike the case of ionic surfactant, with increasing Triton X-100 concentration, the CST of phenol-water system continues to increase and at 0.01 *M* Triton X-100, the CST of the system is very high (>90°). This indicates that in the presence of Triton X-100 solubility of phenol-water decreases.

By analogy with Raoult's expression for the elevation of boiling point, the molecular elevation/depression of critical solution temperature (*E*) may be obtained from the relation³,

$$E = (t-T)/C$$

where, *T* is the critical solution temperature before addition of the surfactant, *t* the critical solution temperature after addition and *C* the concentration of the surfactant in phenol-water system. It can be seen from Table 1 that as the concentration of ionic surfactant is increased, *E* starts decreasing and after certain concentration, it remains practically constant. It is interesting to note that the value corresponding to the concentration obtained from the intersect of the plot of *E* vs concentration of surfactant, nearly equals to that of CMC of that surfactant. We have no explanation for the observed behaviour.

From the present investigation we find that it is possible to have a homogeneous system of partially miscible liquids at room temperature by adding suitable surfactants.

Experimental

Phenol (S.D., A.R.) was used as such. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) (both SISCO) were recrystallized from ethanol-water and dried (m.ps. : 204° and 80° respectively). Triton X-100 (Sigma) and sodium sulfate (S.D., A.R.) were used. Double-distilled water was used for making solutions.

Various solutions of phenol-water system of different compositions were prepared and their miscibility temperatures (average of appearance and disappearance of turbidity of the mixture) were noted (error limit, ±0.2°). Solutions of surfactants and sodium sulfate were prepared in double-distilled water and used to obtain phenol-surfactant solutions.

The mutual solubility curves were obtained by synthetic method.

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